

METHODS OF TEACHING LISTENING IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation

The focus of the article is on the process and methods of mastering listening as a speech and learning activity in elementary school. This article also looks at how to teach listening in primary school English lessons, as well as different forms of listening. Furthermore, this research evaluates the system of auditory activities in English lessons, as well as the technology of teaching listening in English.

Key words: methodology, ESL, primary school, schoolchildren, teaching, listening skill, English language, methods

Listening skill has always been considered as one of the key skills in order to develop successful foreign language competence. Listening is the ability to distinguish and understand what others say, and it is the ability to grasp foreign speech by ear during its transit in relation to educational work in foreign language classes.

This entails being able to recognize the speaker's accent, grammatical structures, and vocabulary. One of the most significant components of teaching foreign language communication is teaching the perception of authentic speech by ear, which is why the invention and development of listening teaching technologies that match the needs of the moment are incredibly vital.

Teaching a foreign language in modern times begins in the second grade, or at the very beginning of study. The first year of secondary school is defined as a period of learning a foreign language that allows students to establish the foundations for communicative competence that are both necessary and sufficient for continued development and improvement in this subject. A sufficiently lengthy period is required to create the foundations of communicative competence, because students must get familiar with the language being studied as a medium of communication from the very beginning.

This means schoolchildren must learn to comprehend foreign speech by ear (listening), to communicate their views through language (speaking), to read, or to understand a foreign text read aloud, and to write, or to be able to convey their thoughts in writing. Furthermore, it is at this time that the methodological framework that serves as the foundation for teaching a foreign language is adopted, allowing the teacher to enter the system and carry out the educational process in line with its primary principles from the beginning.

The uniqueness of early training is that it establishes the perceptual and articulatory foundation for many forms of speech activity, as well as auditory and alphabetic-sound linkages and a limited quantity of language information. The recollection of sound samples from language units and their identification in the flow of speech are the first steps in listening

training. It is vital to encourage youngsters to pay attention to what the teacher or announcer says to them from the very first classes, in order to establish a culture of listening in them.

To summarize the qualities of this stage of learning to listen, I'd like to point out that listening in primary school serves not only as a learning objective, but also as a "powerful" instrument for mastering the sound side of a foreign language, its intonation. The absorption of lexical data and grammatical structures occurs through hearing.

Therefore, learners are introduced to new language or speech material through listening. To structure an introduction to new subject, students must be shown the meaning, form, and application of the topic. When teaching children new vocabulary, it is necessary to repeatedly perceive the form in order for students to master the form; to understand the meaning, you can use a non-translational method of revealing the meaning and only a translation if necessary; and situations are required to illustrate the use of a new word. The perception of the entire, i.e., the statement - a speech unit connected with the circumstance - is the first step in familiarization. As a result, it moves from the general to the specific, from the statement to a single word, and from there to the specific.

Listening is vital in learning a foreign language, especially communicative-oriented learning, because it is intimately tied to other forms of speech activity.

As a result, in the case of early foreign language acquisition, the presentation of hearing materials should begin in the first class so that children can detect speech intonation patterns, hear stressed words, and discern the beginning and end of a phrase. Songs, poetry, and short, comprehensive writings are examples.

However, at this point, the instructor performs the function of the primary native speaker for the kids. Learners are expected to understand his speech, discern between sounds, pronounce words and individual phrases correctly, and have a good grasp of the word as a lexical unit.

Due to a significant number of lexical, grammatical, and phonetic challenges, the use of authentic materials during the early stages of school is limited, whereas fifth-grade pupils already have a sufficient vocabulary that they may safely utilize. As a result, learners should begin purposeful work with audio resources, or the direct execution of a task based on the text they have listened to, when they have a modest vocabulary that they can safely utilize.

The greatest impediment to ear perception of speech is a lack of a linguistic context, as a result of which the sound form of a word takes on less importance than the graphic form, resulting in students failing to identify even words they know how to spell. Students are conditioned to process information primarily through their visual senses. Understanding speech by ear is also objectively limited by auditory perception characteristics such as uniqueness and short duration, which can lead to a breach of perception integrity if particular portions of the message are misread.

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